

This document provides an overview of the directory structures and their contents.

1. Human-Eval-Java-Infill Directory Structure:

The 'src' directory is divided into 'main' and 'test' subdirectories.

- **Main Subdirectory:**
 - **Buggy Directory:** Holds 163 Java files, each with a single masked line indicating a bug.
 - **Correct Directory:** Contains the correct versions of the buggy files.
- **Test Subdirectory:** Contains 163 test suites, each corresponding to one of 163 files in the main subdirectory.

The 'answer' file provides the masked lines for each program. These entries are not in sequential order, but you can easily locate the correct answer by searching for the class name, such as 'ADD_ELEMENTS'.

2. Experiment_Results_Summary:

This directory contains the results of experiments for all 20 models. A pdf file named **Model_Evaluation_Metrics** within the folder provides a detailed description of the metrics used to assess the models' capabilities in generating correct and diverse solutions. It covers model parameters, computational efficiency, output characteristics, and error analysis for both N=1 and N=5. Please refer to the *Model_Evaluation_Metrics* file for a detailed description of these fields.

3. Detailed_Experiment_Outputs:

This directory contains the comprehensive raw data from running each of the 20 models on all 163 buggy programs. It includes the results generated by each model before any analysis or extraction into summarized formats. This raw data serves as the basis for subsequent analysis, leading to the extraction of results provided in the Experiment_Results_Summary directory.

The directory is organised as follows:

- 20 Model Subdirectories: Each subdirectory corresponds to one of the 20 models.
 - Configuration Subdirectories: Within each model subdirectory, there are 28 to 30 subdirectories depending on the model, each representing a different configuration for beam search and nucleus sampling.
 - 5 Result Subdirectories (result0 to result4): Each configuration subdirectory contains five directories named result0 to result4. These directories store the results for five infills for all 163 buggy programs.
 - **results.json:** A summary of results for the infills.

4. Research_Questions_Data_Analysis.xlsx

This Excel file contains extracted data from the results, specifically organized to address research questions and facilitate statistical analysis.